

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_natural_b_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 12:24:52 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	45.20	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.6897	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...x_natural_b_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 12:24:52 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	22.68	μm	
Min:	-11.85	μm	
Max:	10.83	μm	
Size:	328888	digits	
Spacing:	0.06897	nm	
NM-points ratio:	60.24 % (5421835 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 12:24:52 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	22.68	μm	
Size:	328888	digits	
Spacing:	0.06897	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	4.119	μm	
Ssk	-0.4028		
Sku	2.839		
Sp	10.68	μm	
Sv	12.00	μm	
Sz	22.68	μm	
Sa	3.286	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.2358	%	
Smc	4.798	μm	
Sxp	9.455	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	27.20	μm	
Str	0.7231		
Std	3.253	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.6457		
Sdr	15.17	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.1768	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vv	4.975	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmp	0.1768	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmc	3.890	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvc	4.409	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvv	0.5661	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	11.08	µm
Mean depth of furrows	3.267	µm
Mean density of furrows	4139	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	44.99	°
Second direction	0.002021	°
Third direction	90.01	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	79.88	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

